

A Note on the Percentage of Iodine in certain Algae.

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Working on Indian sea-weeds the author found in 1928 that (a) the algae which supply the bulk of the material for the iodine industry in Europe, *vis.*, *Laminaria*, *Fucus serratus* and *Chorda filum*, are absent from Indian waters, and (b) the time for the harvest of sea-weeds was confined to the cold weather. The weed is used as a manure, *e.g.*, for cocoanut trees.

In the winter (February-March) of 1929 the author collected a large amount of different species of algae from various places of the Bombay Presidency from the drift-weed along the shore line. The percentage of iodine calculated for the dry weed (natural drying in air) is recorded below. (For method, see Stanford, *Chem. News*, 1877, 35, 172).

Weed.	Iodine (%).	Place.
<i>Fucus</i> .*	0'027	Porbundar.
<i>Sargassum</i> * ^a	0'032	"
"	0'034	Bombay (Juhu).
"	0'049	Okha.
<i>Asparagopsis saundersiana</i> .	0'092	"
<i>Halymenia</i> .*	0'035	"
<i>Gracilaria</i> * ^a	0'023	"

* Species not determined.

Of the above genera *Sargassum (ginbaso)*, used for the iodine industry in Japan, has been reported by Smith (*Bureau Fisheries Bull.*, 1909, 24, 162) to yield 0'054% and 0'029% of iodine from two localities. The percentage of iodine observed by the author compares favourably with the results of weeds from other countries. The practical difficulties facing its industrial use are twofold, *vis.*, collection, and lack of sufficient quantity of weeds throughout the year.

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